

Evaluating the Impact of Maternal Hypertension on Placental Vascularization and Neonatal Health Outcomes: A Comprehensive Cohort Analysis

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Abstract:

Background: Maternal hypertension is a common pregnancy complication that can adversely affect fetal growth and development.

Aim and Objective: to assess the impact of maternal hypertension on fetal growth parameters and neonatal outcomes.

Materials and Methods: A prospective observational cohort study was conducted from January 2023 to May 2024, involving 200 pregnant women (100 hypertensive and 100 normotensive) at the Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology. Data on maternal characteristics, fetal growth parameters (biparietal diameter, head circumference, abdominal circumference, femur length, and estimated fetal weight), Doppler ultrasound indices (umbilical artery resistance index, pulsatility index, and middle cerebral artery Doppler indices), and neonatal outcomes (birth weight, gestational age, Apgar scores, NICU admissions, and neonatal complications) were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 25.0.

Results: Fetuses of hypertensive mothers showed significantly lower growth parameters compared to those of normotensive mothers: biparietal diameter (87.4 ± 3.2 mm vs. 89.8 ± 3.0 mm, $p < 0.001$), head circumference (308.5 ± 12.4 mm vs. 317.1 ± 11.6 mm, $p < 0.001$), abdominal circumference (280.3 ± 14.1 mm vs. 292.4 ± 13.5 mm, $p < 0.001$), femur length (68.2 ± 2.8 mm vs. 70.1 ± 2.5 mm, $p < 0.001$), and estimated fetal weight (2780 ± 320 g vs. 3050 ± 290 g, $p < 0.001$). Doppler indices indicated higher resistance in the umbilical artery (RI: 0.68 ± 0.05 vs. 0.60 ± 0.04 , $p < 0.001$; PI: 1.35 ± 0.12 vs. 1.18 ± 0.10 , $p < 0.001$) and lower pulsatility in the middle cerebral artery (PI: 1.45 ± 0.10 vs. 1.55 ± 0.12 , $p < 0.001$) in the hypertensive group. Neonates born to hypertensive mothers had lower birth weights (2780 ± 320 g vs. 3050 ± 290 g, $p < 0.001$), lower gestational ages (37.5 ± 2.1 weeks vs. 38.8 ± 1.7 weeks, $p < 0.001$), lower Apgar scores at 1 minute (7.5 ± 1.2 vs. 8.2 ± 1.1 , $p < 0.001$) and 5 minutes (8.5 ± 0.9 vs. 9.0 ± 0.8 , $p < 0.001$), higher NICU admission rates (30% vs. 10%, $p < 0.001$), and more neonatal complications (25% vs. 10%, $p = 0.007$).

Conclusion: Maternal hypertension significantly impairs fetal growth and development, as evidenced by lower fetal growth parameters, altered Doppler indices, and adverse neonatal outcomes. These findings highlight the importance of early detection and management of hypertensive disorders in pregnancy to improve maternal and fetal health.

Keywords: Maternal hypertension, fetal growth, neonatal outcomes, Doppler ultrasound, pregnancy complications.

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Introduction

Maternal hypertension, encompassing conditions such as chronic hypertension, gestational hypertension, and pre-eclampsia, represents a significant clinical challenge in obstetrics. [1] Affecting approximately 5-10% of pregnancies globally, hypertensive disorders are among the leading causes of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. [1,2] The physiological changes

during pregnancy can exacerbate existing hypertension or lead to the development of new hypertensive conditions, complicating the management of both maternal and fetal health. [3, 4]

The impact of maternal hypertension on fetal growth and development has been the subject of

extensive research. [5] Hypertension during pregnancy can impair placental function, reducing blood flow and nutrient supply to the fetus, which may result in intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), low birth weight, preterm birth, and other developmental challenges. [6] Moreover, the long-term effects of compromised fetal development due to maternal hypertension can extend into childhood and adulthood, influencing cognitive development, metabolic health, and cardiovascular function. [5, 7]

Despite advances in prenatal care, the precise mechanisms by which maternal hypertension affects fetal growth and development are not fully understood, and the variability in clinical outcomes suggests a complex interplay of genetic, environmental, and physiological factors. This study aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge by providing a comprehensive analysis of the impact of maternal hypertension on fetal growth parameters and developmental outcomes. By comparing a cohort of hypertensive pregnant women with a control group of normotensive pregnant women, this research seeks to identify specific patterns and predictors of adverse fetal outcomes associated with maternal hypertension.

Understanding these impacts is crucial for developing targeted interventions and improving prenatal care protocols to mitigate the risks associated with hypertensive disorders during pregnancy. The findings of this study have the potential to inform clinical practice and guide future research aimed at enhancing maternal and fetal health outcomes.

Materials and Methods

This study was designed as a prospective observational cohort study conducted over 24 months from January 2023 to May 2024. The Institutional Review Board (IRB) approved the study, and informed consent was obtained from all participants before inclusion in the study.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Pregnant women aged 18-40 years.
2. Singleton pregnancies.
3. Diagnosis of hypertension before or during pregnancy, including chronic hypertension, gestational hypertension, and pre-eclampsia.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Women with pre-existing conditions such as diabetes mellitus, renal disease, or autoimmune disorders.
2. Multiple gestations.
3. Incomplete medical records or loss to follow-up.

Control Group

A control group of normotensive pregnant women matched for age, parity, and gestational age was included for comparison. Normotensive status was confirmed through regular blood pressure measurements throughout the pregnancy.

Data Collection

Data were collected from participants' medical records, prenatal visits, and postpartum follow-ups. The following parameters were recorded:

1. Maternal Data:

- Age
- Parity
- Body Mass Index (BMI)
- Blood pressure readings at multiple gestational ages
- Diagnosis and classification of hypertension
- Medications used for hypertension management
- Presence of any pregnancy-related complications

2. Fetal Data:

- Ultrasound measurements of fetal growth parameters (biparietal diameter, head circumference, abdominal circumference, femur length) at different gestational ages
- Estimated fetal weight (EFW) calculated using standard formulas
- Doppler ultrasound measurements of umbilical artery resistance index (RI), pulsatility index (PI), and middle cerebral artery (MCA) Doppler indices

3. Neonatal Data:

- Birth weight
- Gestational age at birth
- Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes
- Neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) admission
- Presence of any congenital anomalies or neonatal complications

Data Analysis

Data were entered into a secure database and analyzed using SPSS version 25.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) and compared using independent t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests as appropriate. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages

and compared using chi-square or Fisher's exact tests.

Ethical Considerations

The Declaration of Helsinki conducted the study. All participants provided written informed consent. Confidentiality of the participants was maintained by anonymizing data and using secure databases for data storage and analysis.

Results

A total of 200 pregnant women were included in the study: 100 in the hypertensive group and 100 in the normotensive control group. Table 1 summarizes the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Hypertensive Group (n=100)	Normotensive Group (n=100)	p-value
Age (years)	29.4 ± 4.5	28.9 ± 4.3	0.342
Parity (number of pregnancies)	1.7 ± 0.9	1.6 ± 0.8	0.567
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.8 ± 3.4	25.2 ± 2.9	<0.001**
Chronic hypertension (%)	40	0	-
Gestational Hypertension (%)	35	0	-
Pre-eclampsia (%)	25	0	-

**Statistically significant (p<0.05)

Fetal Growth Parameters: The comparison of fetal growth parameters between the hypertensive and normotensive groups is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Fetal Growth Parameters

Parameter	Hypertensive Group (n=100)	Normotensive Group (n=100)	p-value
Biparietal Diameter (mm)	87.4 ± 3.2	89.8 ± 3.0	<0.001**
Head Circumference (mm)	308.5 ± 12.4	317.1 ± 11.6	<0.001**
Abdominal circumference (mm)	280.3 ± 14.1	292.4 ± 13.5	<0.001**
Femur Length (mm)	68.2 ± 2.8	70.1 ± 2.5	<0.001**
Estimated Fetal Weight (g)	2780 ± 320	3050 ± 290	<0.001**

**Statistically significant (p<0.05)

Doppler Ultrasound Indices: The Doppler ultrasound indices for the umbilical and middle cerebral arteries are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Doppler Ultrasound Indices

Parameter	Hypertensive Group (n=100)	Normotensive Group (n=100)	p-value
Umbilical Artery RI	0.68 ± 0.05	0.60 ± 0.04	<0.001**
Umbilical Artery PI	1.35 ± 0.12	1.18 ± 0.10	<0.001**
MCA Doppler PI	1.45 ± 0.10	1.55 ± 0.12	<0.001**

**Statistically significant (p<0.05)

Neonatal Outcomes: Table 4 presents the neonatal outcomes, including birth weight, gestational age at birth, Apgar scores, NICU admission rates, and neonatal complications.

Table 4: Neonatal Outcomes

Outcome	Hypertensive Group (n=100)	Normotensive Group (n=100)	p-value
Birth Weight (g)	2780 ± 320	3050 ± 290	<0.001**
Gestational Age at Birth (weeks)	37.5 ± 2.1	38.8 ± 1.7	<0.001**
Apgar Score at 1 min	7.5 ± 1.2	8.2 ± 1.1	<0.001**
Apgar Score at 5 min	8.5 ± 0.9	9.0 ± 0.8	<0.001**
NICU Admission (%)	30	10	<0.001**
Neonatal Complications (%)	25	10	0.007**

**Statistically significant (p<0.05)

Discussion

This study demonstrates that maternal hypertension significantly impacts fetal growth and development. Fetuses of hypertensive mothers showed lower growth parameters, such as biparietal diameter, head circumference, abdominal circumference, femur length, and estimated fetal weight. Addition-

ally, Doppler ultrasound indices indicated compromised placental function and neonatal outcomes were poorer in terms of birth weight, gestational age, Apgar scores, NICU admissions, and neonatal complications.

Our findings are consistent with previous research indicating the detrimental effects of maternal hy-

pertension on fetal growth and development. For instance, a study by Zhang et al. (2017) [8] found that hypertensive disorders during pregnancy are strongly associated with intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) and low birth weight. Similarly, Roberts and Gammill (2005) [9] reported that preeclampsia, a severe form of hypertensive disorder, leads to reduced uteroplacental blood flow, contributing to fetal growth restriction.

The Doppler ultrasound findings in our study align with those reported by Sibai et al. (2000) [10], who observed increased resistance indices in the umbilical artery and altered cerebral blood flow in fetuses of hypertensive mothers, suggesting placental insufficiency. These alterations in blood flow patterns reflect the fetus's adaptive mechanisms to chronic hypoxia, prioritizing vital organs such as the brain.

Mechanisms and Pathophysiology

The pathophysiological mechanisms underlying the adverse effects of maternal hypertension on fetal growth are multifaceted. Hypertensive disorders can lead to impaired trophoblast invasion and abnormal remodelling of the spiral arteries, resulting in reduced uteroplacental perfusion. This insufficiency in placental blood flow decreases the supply of oxygen and nutrients to the fetus, thereby hindering growth and development. [11]

Oxidative stress and inflammation are also critical factors in the pathogenesis of hypertensive disorders during pregnancy. Elevated levels of circulating antiangiogenic factors such as soluble fms-like tyrosine kinase-1 (sFlt-1) and endoglin disrupt endothelial function and angiogenesis, exacerbating placental dysfunction and contributing to fetal growth restriction. [4, 11]

Clinical Implications

The findings of this study highlight the importance of early identification and management of hypertensive disorders in pregnancy. Regular prenatal care, including blood pressure monitoring and ultrasound assessments, is crucial for detecting and managing hypertension to mitigate its impact on fetal growth. Interventions such as antihypertensive medications, lifestyle modifications, and timely delivery planning can improve maternal and fetal outcomes.

Additionally, our results underscore the need for postnatal follow-up of infants born to hypertensive mothers, as they may be at increased risk for long-term developmental and health issues. Early intervention programs and routine health checks can help address potential complications and support optimal growth and development in these infants.

Strengths and Limitations

A key strength of this study is its comprehensive analysis of fetal growth parameters and Doppler ultrasound indices, providing a detailed assessment of the impact of maternal hypertension. The prospective design and the use of a well-matched control group enhance the validity of the findings.

However, this study has some limitations. While the sample size is adequate, it may limit the generalizability of the results to broader populations. Additionally, the study did not account for potential confounding factors such as maternal diet, socioeconomic status, and genetic predispositions, which could influence fetal growth and development.

Future Research Directions

Further research is needed to elucidate the molecular mechanisms underlying the impact of maternal hypertension on fetal development. Longitudinal studies following infants exposed to hypertensive conditions in utero into childhood and adulthood can provide valuable insights into the long-term health consequences.

Exploring potential interventions to improve placental function and mitigate the adverse effects of hypertension on fetal growth is also a crucial area for future investigation. Advances in personalized medicine and targeted therapies hold promise for enhancing the management of hypertensive disorders in pregnancy and improving maternal and fetal outcomes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, maternal hypertension poses significant risks to fetal growth and development, as evidenced by lower fetal growth parameters, altered Doppler ultrasound indices, and poorer neonatal outcomes. These findings underscore the need for vigilant prenatal care, early identification and management of hypertensive disorders, and postnatal follow-up of affected infants. Enhanced understanding of the pathophysiological mechanisms and development of targeted interventions are essential for improving the health and well-being of both mother and child.

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